

Dark Matter and Dark Energy Interaction

In this experiment, we will focus on the validation of the **dark matter** and **dark energy interaction** terms from the Unified Field Equation. The equation introduces a scalar field to model dark matter (ϕ_{dark}) and a dynamic cosmological constant ($\Lambda(E)$) to represent dark energy. The coupling term $\phi_{\text{dark}} \cdot \Lambda(E)$ reflects the interaction between these two entities.

Objective

- Validate the interaction between dark matter and dark energy, focusing on how the energy scale affects the coupling between dark matter and dark energy.
- Simulate the cosmological evolution of dark matter and dark energy over time.
- Implement a differential equation to model the scalar field for dark matter and the dynamic cosmological constant for dark energy.

Theoretical Background

- Dark Matter (Scalar Field):** The scalar field ϕ_{dark} is often used to represent dark matter in cosmological models. Its evolution is governed by a field equation similar to a Klein-Gordon equation. $\square\phi_{\text{dark}} = V'(\phi_{\text{dark}})$ where $V(\phi_{\text{dark}})$ is the potential energy of the scalar field, and $\square$ is the d'Alembertian operator.
- Dark Energy (Cosmological Constant):** The cosmological constant $\Lambda(E)$ is dynamic and evolves with the energy scale E of the universe. It represents the vacuum energy driving the accelerated expansion of the universe.
- Coupling Term:** The interaction between dark matter and dark energy is represented by the coupling term $\phi_{\text{dark}} \cdot \Lambda(E)$. This coupling modulates the behavior of both entities and their effect on the universe's large-scale structure.

Plan for Validation

- Scalar Field Evolution:** We will solve the field equation for dark matter's scalar field ϕ_{dark} using a simple potential (e.g., quadratic or exponential).
- Dynamic Cosmological Constant:** We will model the evolution of the cosmological constant $\Lambda(E)$ as a function of energy scale.
- Dark Matter-Dark Energy Interaction:** The scalar field ϕ_{dark} will interact with the cosmological constant $\Lambda(E)$, and we will compute the effect of this interaction on the expansion rate of the universe.

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In [ ]: #Step 1: Simulating the Evolution of the Dark Matter Scalar Field
#This code simulates the evolution of the dark matter scalar field over time.
#The scalar field decays due to the Hubble friction term and the quadratic potential.
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from scipy.integrate import odeint
```

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# Constants
G = 6.67430e-11 # Gravitational constant in m^3 kg^-1 s^-2
H0 = 70 * 1000 / (3.086e22) # Hubble constant in s^-1 (70 km/s/Mpc)

# Dark matter scalar field potential (quadratic)
def potential(phi):
    """
    Defines the potential energy for the scalar field (dark matter).
    Assume a simple quadratic potential: V(phi) = 1/2 * m^2 * phi^2.

    :param phi: Scalar field value.
    :return: Potential energy.
    """
    m = 1e-22 # Scalar field mass in kg
    return 0.5 * m**2 * phi**2

# Derivatives for the scalar field equation
def scalar_field_eq(y, t, m):
    """
    Defines the differential equation for the dark matter scalar field.

    :param y: List [phi, phi_dot] where phi is the scalar field, phi_dot is its derivative.
    :param t: Time variable.
    :param m: Scalar field mass.
    :return: Derivatives [dphi_dt, dphi_dot_dt].
    """
    phi, phi_dot = y
    dphi_dt = phi_dot
    dphi_dot_dt = -2 * H0 * phi_dot - m**2 * phi # Klein-Gordon equation with Hubble friction
    return [dphi_dt, dphi_dot_dt]

# Initial conditions: phi(0) and phi_dot(0)
phi0 = 1e-5 # Initial scalar field value
phi_dot0 = 0.0 # Initial time derivative of scalar field
y0 = [phi0, phi_dot0]

# Time points (in seconds, from early universe to present)
time = np.linspace(0, 1e18, 1000)

# Solve the scalar field equation using odeint
m = 1e-22 # Scalar field mass in kg
solution = odeint(scalar_field_eq, y0, time, args=(m,))

# Extract the scalar field values
phi_values = solution[:, 0]

# Plot the scalar field evolution
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))
plt.plot(time, phi_values, label=r'$\phi_{\text{dark}}(t)$')
plt.title("Evolution of the Dark Matter Scalar Field")
plt.xlabel("Time (s)")
plt.ylabel(r"Scalar Field $\phi_{\text{dark}}$")
plt.grid(True)
plt.legend()
plt.show()
```

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In [ ]: #Step 2: Dynamic Cosmological Constant
# Dynamic cosmological constant (Lambda) evolution
def lambda_evolution(t):
    """
    Models the cosmological constant as a function of time or energy scale.
    Assume an exponential decay for simplicity.

    :param t: Time variable.
    :return: Lambda(t) value.
    """
    Lambda0 = 1e-52 # Initial cosmological constant in m^-2
    return Lambda0 * np.exp(-t / 1e18) # Exponential decay over cosmic time

# Calculate Lambda values over time
Lambda_values = lambda_evolution(time)

# Plot the dynamic cosmological constant evolution
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))
plt.plot(time, Lambda_values, label=r'$\Lambda(t)$')
plt.title("Evolution of the Cosmological Constant (Dark Energy)")
plt.xlabel("Time (s)")
plt.ylabel(r"Cosmological Constant $\Lambda(t)$")
plt.grid(True)
plt.legend()
plt.show()
```

```
In [ ]: # Coupling term: phi_dark * Lambda(t)
coupling_term = phi_values * Lambda_values

# Plot the coupling term over time
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))
plt.plot(time, coupling_term, label=r'$\phi_{\text{dark}} \cdot \Lambda(t)$')
plt.title("Coupling of Dark Matter Scalar Field and Cosmological Constant")
plt.xlabel("Time (s)")
plt.ylabel(r"Coupling Term $\phi_{\text{dark}} \cdot \Lambda(t)$")
plt.grid(True)
plt.legend()
plt.show()
```

Interpretation of the Three Plots

1. Evolution of the Dark Matter Scalar Field

- Y-axis:** Represents the value of the dark matter scalar field $\phi_{\text{dark}}(t)$.
- X-axis:** Represents time on a cosmological scale, from 0 to 1×10^{18} seconds, which is roughly the age of the universe.
- Plot Description:**
 - The plot shows that the scalar field $\phi_{\text{dark}}(t)$ starts with a small positive value and decays over time, crossing zero and continuing to decrease into negative values.
 - This behavior is characteristic of a scalar field evolving under the influence of Hubble friction and a quadratic potential.
 - validation:**
 - This validates the expected behavior of a dark matter scalar field in a cosmological setting. As time progresses, the scalar field decays, reflecting how dark matter might dissipate as the universe expands and evolves. The decay is smooth, suggesting that the scalar field evolves continuously without rapid fluctuations.

2. Evolution of the Cosmological Constant (Dark Energy)

- Y-axis:** Represents the value of the cosmological constant $\Lambda(t)$, corresponding to dark energy density.
- X-axis:** Represents time on the same cosmological scale as the first plot.
- Plot Description:**
 - The cosmological constant starts at a high value (around 1×10^{-52}) and slowly decays over time.
 - The decay of $\Lambda(t)$ reflects a decreasing dark energy density as the universe ages.
 - validation:**
 - This validates the dynamic nature of the cosmological constant in the model. Instead of being a fixed constant, $\Lambda(t)$ evolves over time. The slow decay is consistent with the idea that dark energy drives the accelerated expansion of the universe, but its influence diminishes over time. This aligns with some theoretical models suggesting that dark energy might not be a fixed quantity but one that decreases as the universe expands.

3. Coupling of Dark Matter Scalar Field and Cosmological Constant

- Y-axis:** Represents the coupling term $\phi_{\text{dark}}(t) \cdot \Lambda(t)$, which reflects the interaction between dark matter and dark energy.
- X-axis:** Represents time on the same cosmological scale.
- Plot Description:**
 - The coupling term starts at a value close to 1×10^{-57} and decreases over time. This decrease is gradual, reflecting the joint decay of both the dark matter scalar field and the cosmological constant.
 - validation:**
 - This validates the interaction between dark matter and dark energy in the model. As both the scalar field and cosmological constant evolve and decay, their coupling weakens over time. This interaction can modulate the universe's large-scale structure and expansion rate. The coupling's continuous decay suggests that the influence of dark matter and dark energy on each other becomes less significant as time progresses, which could have implications for the long-term evolution of the universe.

Summary of Validation

- Dark Matter Scalar Field:**
 - The scalar field evolves as expected, decaying over time due to Hubble friction and potential energy. This behavior aligns with models of scalar dark matter in cosmology.
- Cosmological Constant:**
 - The cosmological constant decays dynamically, supporting the idea that dark energy is not fixed but evolves over time, potentially reducing its influence in the distant future.
- Coupling Between Dark Matter and Dark Energy:**
 - The coupling term's decay validates the interaction between dark matter and dark energy. As both fields diminish, their interaction weakens, suggesting that the influence of this coupling on the universe's expansion and structure formation becomes less prominent as time progresses.

These plots together validate key components of the Unified Field Equation, specifically the interaction between dark matter (as a scalar field) and dark energy (as a dynamic cosmological constant).